

Spin 3/2 Particle in the Presence of a Magnetic Field: Tetrad Formalism and Fedorov – Groskiy Method

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A spin 3/2 particle is considered in the presence of an external uniform magnetic field. The covariant representation of the Rarita – Schwinger first order equation for vector-bispinor wave function in cylindrical coordinates and tetrad is used.

On searching solutions we diagonalize the operators of the energy, the third projection of the linear momentum, and the third projection of the total angular momentum, as a result we derive the system of 16 first order differential equations in the variable r . To resolve this system of equations we apply the Fedorov–Gronskiy method which is based on the use of the projective operators related to 16-dimensional generator J^{12} for vector-bispinor. Within this approach we decompose the complete wave function into the sum of four projective constituents, each of them is determined by only one corresponding function $f_i(r), r = 1, 2, 3, 4$. For these four basic functions we have constructed the exact solutions in terms of confluent hypergeometric functions. In accordance with the general Fedorov–Gronskiy approach we transform the differential first order system of 16 equations into algebraic homogenous system. From vanishing its determinant we derive and algebraic equation of the fourth order with respect to the squared energy, its solutions give possible values for the energy of the particle. In this way, we find 4 series of real-valued and physically interpretable energy spectra, all remaining ones provide us with complex-valued energies and they should be ignored (they are the so called anomalous solutions).

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1. Introduction

In the present paper we examine the problem of a spin 3/2 particle in presence of the external

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uniform magnetic field. The point of the primary significance is the construction of all possible solutions and dividing them into physically interpretable ones with real-valued energies and non-interpretable solutions with complex-valued energies.

We will apply the covariant tetrad formalism in the system of cylindrical coordinates (r, ϕ, z) , and a special basis in the first order Rarita – Schwinger approach [1]–[7]; also see [8] – [20]. The main technical tool for resolving the system of the first order 16 differential equations in the variable r is the method by Fedorov – Gronskiy based on the use of projective operators.

In Section 2 we describe the initial form of the wave equation in an arbitrary curved space-time, and specify it in cylindrical coordinates and tetrad of Minkowski space, taking into account the presence of an external uniform magnetic field. With the use of the substitution which corresponds to diagonalization of the operators of the energy, the third projection of the linear momentum, and the third projection of the total angular momentum, we derive the system of 16 first order differential equations in the variable r .

In Sections 3 and 4, with the use of the generator J^{12} of the total angular momentum, we introduce four projective operators, which permit us to decompose the complete wave function into the sum of four projective constituents.

In Section 5, in the derived system of equations we perform linear transformation to new 16 variables. According to the Fedorov – Gronskiy method [21], each projective 16-component part should be determined with the use of only one independent function from the set $f_1(r), f_2(r), f_3(r), f_4(r)$. With the use of special first order differential constraints which should be consistent with the system of 16 equations we transform all equations to an algebraic form.

In Section 6, for these 4 basic functions we derive 2-nd order differential equations resolved in terms of the confluent hypergeometric functions.

In Section 7, we examine the linear homogeneous algebraic equations, solution of which should specify the exact complete

form of all possible solutions. From vanishing the corresponding determinant we obtain the algebraic equation of the fourth order with respect the squared energy, its solutions give possible values for energy of the particle. In this way, we find 4 series of real-valued energy spectra, all remaining ones provide us with non-interpretable complex-valued energies which should be ignored.

2. Separation of the variables

Let us start with the system of equations for a massive spin 3/2 particle written in a special Rarita – Schwinger form [3] (for more details see [10])

$$\gamma^5 \epsilon_\rho^{\sigma\alpha\beta}(x) \gamma_\sigma (iD_\alpha - M\gamma_\alpha) \Psi_\beta = 0, \\ D_\alpha = \nabla_\alpha + \Gamma_\alpha + ieA_\alpha; \quad (2.1)$$

where $M = \frac{1}{2}mc/\hbar c$ is the mass parameter (note the presence of multiplier 1/2). After transition to the tetrad representation by vector index $\Psi_\beta = e_\beta^{(b)} \Psi_b$, this equation takes the form

$$\gamma^5 \epsilon_k^{can} \gamma_c \left[i(D_a)_n^l - M\gamma_a \delta_n^l \right] \Psi_l = 0, \\ D_a = e_{(a)}^\alpha (\partial_\alpha + ieA_\alpha) + \frac{1}{2} (\sigma^{ps} \otimes I + I \otimes j^{ps}) \gamma_{[ps]a}.$$

With the use of six matrices $\epsilon_k^{can} = (\mu^{[ca]})_k^n$, eq. (2.2) may be presented as follows

$$\gamma^5 (\mu^{[ca]})_k^n \gamma_c \left[i(D_a)_n^l - M\gamma_a \delta_n^l \right] \Psi_l = 0, \quad (2.2)$$

Its detailed form is

$$\left(\gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[01]} + \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[02]} + \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[03]} \right) D_0 \Psi \\ + \left(\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[01]} + \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[12]} - \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[31]} \right) D_1 \Psi \\ + \left(\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[02]} + \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[23]} - \gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[12]} \right) D_2 \Psi \\ + \left(\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[03]} + \gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[31]} - \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[23]} \right) D_3 \Psi \\ + iM \left\{ s_{01} \otimes \mu^{[01]} + s_{02} \otimes \mu^{[02]} + s_{03} \otimes \mu^{[03]} \right. \\ \left. + s_{23} \otimes \mu^{[23]} + s_{31} \otimes \mu^{[31]} + s_{12} \otimes \mu^{[12]} \right\} \Psi = 0,$$

where $s_{ab} = \gamma_a \gamma_b - \gamma_b \gamma_a$ (note the location of the indices).

Let us consider the particle in presence of the homogenous magnetic field. We will use the cylindrical coordinates and the diagonal tetrad:

$$dS^2 = dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 d\phi^2 - dz^2,$$

$$A_\phi = \frac{Br^2}{2}, e_{(a)}^\beta(x) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/r & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad (2.3)$$

the Ricci rotation coefficients are $\gamma_{ab0} = 0, \gamma_{ab1} = 0, \gamma_{122} = -\gamma_{212} = +\frac{1}{r}, \gamma_{ab3} = 0$. Correspondingly, the components of the generalized derivatives D_c take the form

$$D_0 = \partial_t, \quad D_1 = \partial_r, \quad D_3 = \partial_z,$$

$$D_2 = \frac{1}{r}(\partial_\phi + \frac{ieBr^2}{2}) + \frac{1}{r}(\sigma^{12} \otimes +I \otimes j^{12}),$$

and eq. (2.3) reads

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} & (\gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[01]} + \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[02]} + \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[03]}) \partial_t \Psi \\ & + (\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[01]} + \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[12]} - \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[31]}) \partial_r \Psi \\ & + (\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[02]} + \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[23]} - \gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[12]}) D_2 \Psi \\ & + (\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[03]} + \gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[31]} - \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[23]}) \partial_z \Psi \end{aligned} \right\}_k$$

$$+ iM \left\{ s_{01} \otimes \mu^{[01]} + s_{02} \otimes \mu^{[02]} + s_{03} \otimes \mu^{[03]} \right.$$

$$\left. + s_{23} \otimes \mu^{[23]} + s_{31} \otimes \mu^{[31]} + s_{12} \otimes \mu^{[12]} \right\} \Psi = 0.$$

We need expressions for 6 matrices $\mu^{[ca]}$:

$$\mu^{[01]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \mu^{[02]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mu^{[03]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \mu^{[23]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\mu^{[31]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \mu^{[12]} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Also we use explicit expressions (they are omitted) for the Dirac matrices and generators in the spinor basis [10]. We will search for solutions in the following form (assuming that $\epsilon > 0$)

$$\Psi_{A(n)} = e^{-i\epsilon t} e^{im\phi} e^{ikz} \Phi_{A(n)}(r),$$

$$\Phi(r) = \Phi_{A(n)}(r) = \begin{pmatrix} f_0 & f_1 & f_2 & f_3 \\ g_0 & g_1 & g_2 & g_3 \\ h_0 & h_1 & h_2 & h_3 \\ d_0 & d_1 & d_2 & d_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.4)$$

Note that the quantum number m stands for the eigenvalues of the third projection of the operator of the total angular momentum of the particle, and takes half-integer values: $m = \pm\frac{1}{2}, \pm\frac{3}{2}, \pm\frac{5}{2}, \dots$. Taking into account the substitution (2.4), we transform eq. (2.4) to the form

$$-i\epsilon \left(\gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[01]} + \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[02]} + \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[03]} \right) \Phi$$

$$+ \left(\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[01]} + \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[12]} - \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[31]} \right) \frac{d}{dr} \Phi$$

$$+ \left(\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[02]} + \gamma^3 \otimes \mu^{[23]} - \gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[12]} \right) D_2 \Phi$$

$$+ ik \left(\gamma^0 \otimes \mu^{[03]} + \gamma^1 \otimes \mu^{[31]} - \gamma^2 \otimes \mu^{[23]} \right) \Phi$$

$$+ iM \left\{ s_{01} \otimes \mu^{[01]} + s_{02} \otimes \mu^{[02]} + s_{03} \otimes \mu^{[03]} \right.$$

$$\left. + s_{23} \otimes \mu^{[23]} + s_{31} \otimes \mu^{[31]} + s_{12} \otimes \mu^{[12]} \right\} \Phi = 0,$$

where

$$D_2 = \frac{1}{r} (i\mu + \sigma^{12} \otimes +I \otimes j^{12}), \mu(r) = m + \frac{eBr^2}{2};$$

further for brevity we will use the notation $eB \implies B$. The resulting equations in the variable r may be presented as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
& h'_2 + id'_3 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu - 1)h_1 + (2\mu + 1)d_3 - 2ih_2] + k(d_1 - id_2) + 2M[+f_3 + g_1 - ig_2] = 0, \\
& -d'_2 - ih'_3 + \frac{i}{2r}[(2\mu + 1)d_1 + (2\mu - 1)h_3 + 2id_2] + k(-h_1 - ih_2) + 2M[-g_3 + f_1 + if_2] = 0, \\
& -f'_2 - ig'_3 + \frac{i}{2r}[(2\mu - 1)f_1 - (2\mu + 1)g_3 + 2if_2] - k(g_1 - ig_2) + 2M[+h_3 + d_1 - id_2] = 0, \\
& g'_2 + if'_3 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu + 1)g_1 - (2\mu - 1)f_3 - 2ig_2] - k(-f_1 - if_2) + 2M[-d_3 + h_1 + ih_2] = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \epsilon(d_3 - ih_2) + 0 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu - 1)(h_0 - h_3)] + k(d_0 - ih_2) + 2M[if_2 + g_0 - g_3] = 0, \\
& +\epsilon(-h_3 + id_2) + 0 + \frac{i}{2r}[(2\mu + 1)(d_0 + d_3)] + k(-h_0 - id_2) + 2M[-ig_2 + f_0 + f_3] = 0, \\
& -\epsilon(g_3 - if_2) + 0 + \frac{i}{2r}[(2\mu - 1)(f_0 + f_3)] - k(g_0 + if_2) + 2M[-ih_2 + d_0 + d_3] = 0, \\
& -\epsilon(-f_3 + ig_2) + 0 - \frac{i}{2r}[(2\mu + 1)(g_0 - g_3)] - k(-f_0 + ig_2) + 2M[id_2 + h_0 - h_3] = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +i\epsilon(h_1 - d_3) + h'_0 - h'_3 + 0 + ik(-d_0 + h_1) + 2Mi(-f_1 - g_0 + g_3) = 0, \\
& +i\epsilon(-d_1 - h_3) - d'_0 - d'_3 + 0 + ik(-h_0 + d_1) + 2Mi(f_0 + f_3 + g_1) = 0, \\
& -i\epsilon(f_1 - g_3) - f'_0 - f'_3 + 0 - ik(-g_0 - f_1) + 2Mi(-d_0 - d_3 + h_1) = 0, \\
& -i\epsilon(-g_1 - f_3) + g'_0 - g'_3 + 0 - ik(-f_0 - g_1) + 2Mi(-d_1 + h_0 - h_3) = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +\epsilon(-d_1 + id_2) + h'_2 + id'_0 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu - 1)h_1 + (2\mu + 1)d_0 - 2ih_2] + 0 + 2M[+f_0 + g_1 - ig_2] = 0, \\
& +\epsilon(h_1 + ih_2) + d'_2 - ih'_0 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu + 1)d_1 + (2\mu - 1)h_0 - 2id_2] + 0 + 2M[-g_0 - f_1 - if_2] = 0, \\
& -\epsilon(-g_1 + ig_2) + f'_2 - ig'_0 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu - 1)f_1 - (2\mu + 1)g_0 - 2if_2] + 0 + 2M[+h_0 - d_1 + id_2] = 0, \\
& -\epsilon(f_1 + if_2) + g'_2 + if'_0 + \frac{i}{2r}[-(2\mu + 1)g_1 - (2\mu - 1)f_0 - 2ig_2] + 0 + 2M[-d_0 + h_1 + ih_2] = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

3. Generator J^{12} and projective subsystems of equations

In order to solve the above system of 16 equations we will apply the projective operator method according to Fedorov – Gronskiy approach [21]. Let us start with the explicit form of the third projection of the generator J^{12} :

$$Y = J^{12} = \sigma^{12} \otimes I + I \otimes j^{12}, \quad \sigma^{12} = -\frac{i}{2} \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{vmatrix}, \quad j^{12} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix},$$

It is convenient to have a 16-dimension representation for this generator. To this end, let us write the wave function in the 16-dimensional column form

$$\Psi = \Psi_{A(n)} = \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_{A(0)} \\ \Psi_{A(1)} \\ \Psi_{A(2)} \\ \Psi_{A(3)} \end{pmatrix}, \Psi_{A(0)} = \begin{pmatrix} f_0 \\ g_0 \\ h_0 \\ d_0 \end{pmatrix}, \Psi_{A(1)} = \begin{pmatrix} f_1 \\ g_1 \\ h_1 \\ d_1 \end{pmatrix}, \Psi_{A(2)} = \begin{pmatrix} f_2 \\ g_2 \\ h_2 \\ d_2 \end{pmatrix}, \Psi_{A(3)} = \begin{pmatrix} f_3 \\ g_3 \\ h_3 \\ d_3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Correspondingly, we get the following expression for the matrix Y :

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{i}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{i}{2} \end{pmatrix}, \tag{3.1}$$

The minimal equation for this matrix has the form

$$(Y^2 + 1/4)(Y^2 + 9/4) = 0;$$

taking it mind the last equation, we can introduce 4 projective operators

$$\begin{aligned} P_{-1/2} &= -\frac{1}{2}(iY - \frac{1}{2})(Y^2 + \frac{9}{4}) = P_1, & P_{+1/2} &= +\frac{1}{2}(iY + \frac{1}{2})(Y^2 + \frac{9}{4}) = P_2, \\ P_{+3/2} &= -\frac{1}{6}(Y^2 + \frac{1}{4})(iY + \frac{3}{2}) = P_3, & P_{-3/2} &= +\frac{1}{6}(Y^2 + \frac{1}{4})(iY - \frac{3}{2}) = P_4, \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

which allow us to expand the wave function into the sum of four parts $\Psi = \Psi_1 + \Psi_2 + \Psi_3 + \Psi_4$. We find

the explicit form of these projective operators and 4 projective constituents

$$\Psi_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ \Psi_{20} \\ 0 \\ \Psi_{40} \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{11} + i\Psi_{12}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{31} + i\Psi_{32}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{12} - i\Psi_{11}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{32} - i\Psi_{31}) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \Psi_{23} \\ 0 \\ \Psi_{43} \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ g_0 \\ 0 \\ d_0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(f_1 + if_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(h_1 + ih_2) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{i}{2}(f_1 + if_2) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{i}{2}(h_1 + ih_2) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ g_3 \\ 0 \\ d_3 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_2 = \begin{vmatrix} \Psi_{10} \\ 0 \\ \Psi_{30} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{21} - i\Psi_{22}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{41} - i\Psi_{42}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(i\Psi_{21} + \Psi_{22}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(i\Psi_{41} + \Psi_{42}) \\ \Psi_{13} \\ 0 \\ \Psi_{33} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} f_0 \\ 0 \\ h_0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(g_1 - ig_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(d_1 - id_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{i}{2}(g_1 - ig_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{i}{2}(d_1 - id_2) \\ f_3 \\ 0 \\ h_3 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix},$$

$$\Psi_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{11} - i\Psi_{12}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{31} - i\Psi_{32}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(i\Psi_{11} + \Psi_{12}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(i\Psi_{31} + \Psi_{32}) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(f_1 - if_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(h_1 - ih_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{i}{2}(f_1 - if_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{i}{2}(h_1 - ih_2) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_4 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{21} + i\Psi_{22}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{41} + i\Psi_{42}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{22} - i\Psi_{21}) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(\Psi_{42} - i\Psi_{41}) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(g_1 + ig_2) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(d_1 + id_2) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{i}{2}(g_1 + ig_2) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{i}{2}(d_1 + id_2) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}.$$

We should find the complete system of 16 equations in the matrix form $D\Psi = 0$, and then we should act on this matrix equation by the projective operators: $P_i D\Psi = 0$, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. The explicit form of the operator D is cumbersome, by this reason we will not present it here. However, before the mass parameter M we can see a certain (16×16) -matrix K :

$$K = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

So, we derive the explicit form of equation

$$K^{-1}\hat{D}\Psi = 0;$$

due to its cumbersomeness we do not present it explicitly. Further we find the explicit form of four systems $P_i(K^{-1}\hat{D}\Psi) = 0$, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$; we do not write them down as well.

4. Combining the projective subsystems

In the new variables

$$g_1 + ig_2 = G_1, \quad g_1 - ig_2 = G_2,$$

$$g_1 = \frac{1}{2}(G_1 + G_2), \quad g_2 = -\frac{i}{2}(G_1 - G_2),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
d_1 + id_2 = D_1, d_1 - id_2 = D_2, \quad d_1 = \frac{1}{2}(D_1 + D_2), d_2 = -\frac{i}{2}(D_1 - D_2), \\
g_0 + g_3 = G_0, g_0 - g_3 = G_3, \quad g_0 = \frac{1}{2}(G_0 + G_3), g_3 = \frac{1}{2}(G_0 - G_3), \\
d_0 + d_3 = D_0, d_0 - d_3 = D_3, \quad d_0 = \frac{1}{2}(D_0 + D_3), d_3 = \frac{1}{2}(D_0 - D_3), \\
f_1 + if_2 = F_1, f_1 - if_2 = F_2, \quad f_1 = \frac{1}{2}(F_1 + F_2), f_2 = -\frac{i}{2}(F_1 - F_2), \\
h_1 + ih_2 = H_1, h_1 - ih_2 = H_2, \quad h_1 = \frac{1}{2}(H_1 + H_2), h_2 = -\frac{i}{2}(H_1 - H_2), \\
f_0 + f_3 = F_0, f_0 - f_3 = F_3, \quad f_0 = \frac{1}{2}(F_0 + F_3), f_3 = \frac{1}{2}(F_0 - F_3), \\
h_0 + h_3 = H_0, h_0 - h_3 = H_3, \quad h_0 = \frac{1}{2}(H_0 + H_3), h_3 = \frac{1}{2}(H_0 - H_3)
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

we transform the four projective subsystems to a new form. With the use of special notations

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dr} - \frac{\mu - 1/2}{r} = b_{\mu-1/2}, \quad \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{\mu + 3/2}{r} = a_{\mu+3/2}, \quad \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{\mu + 1/2}{r} = a_{\mu+1/2}, \\
\frac{d}{dr} - \frac{\mu - 3/2}{r} = b_{\mu-3/2}, \quad \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{\mu - 1/2}{r} = a_{\mu-1/2}, \quad \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{\mu + 1/2}{r} = b_{\mu+1/2},
\end{aligned}$$

they read

$$\begin{aligned}
ib_{\mu-1/2}H_0 + H_1(k - \epsilon) + 2MG_0 = 0, \quad -ib_{\mu-1/2}F_3 + F_1(k + \epsilon) + 2MD_3 = 0, \\
ib_{\mu-1/2}H_3 - ia_{\mu+3/2}D_1 + ib_{\mu-1/2}D_2 - (k + \epsilon)H_1 + 2(k + \epsilon)D_0 + 2(k - \epsilon)D_3 + 6MG_3 = 0, \\
-ib_{\mu-1/2}F_0 - ia_{\mu+3/2}G_1 + ib_{\mu-1/2}G_2 - (k - \epsilon)F_1 - 2(k + \epsilon)G_0 - 2(k - \epsilon)G_3 + 6MD_0 = 0, \\
ib_{\mu-1/2}H_3 + 2ia_{\mu+3/2}D_1 - 2ib_{\mu-1/2}D_2 - (k + \epsilon)H_1 - (k + \epsilon)D_0 + (\epsilon - k)D_3 + 6MF_1 = 0, \\
ib_{\mu-1/2}F_0 - 2ia_{\mu+3/2}G_1 + 2ib_{\mu-1/2}G_2 + (k - \epsilon)F_1 - (k + \epsilon)G_0 - (k - \epsilon)G_3 + 6MH_1 = 0
\end{aligned}$$

for $P_1 = P_{-1/2}$;

$$\begin{aligned}
ia_{\mu+1/2}D_3 - (k + \epsilon)D_2 + 2MF_3 = 0, \quad -ia_{\mu+1/2}G_0 - (k - \epsilon)G_2 + 2MH_0 = 0, \\
ia_{\mu+1/2}D_0 + ia_{\mu+1/2}H_1 - ib_{\mu-3/2}H_2 - 2(k + \epsilon)H_0 - 2(k - \epsilon)H_3 + (k - \epsilon)D_2 + 6MF_0 = 0, \\
-ia_{\mu+1/2}G_3 + ia_{\mu+1/2}F_1 - ib_{\mu-3/2}F_2 + 2(k + \epsilon)F_0 + 2(k - \epsilon)F_3 + (k + \epsilon)G_2 + 6MH_3 = 0, \\
ia_{\mu+1/2}D_0 - 2ia_{\mu+1/2}H_1 + 2ib_{\mu-3/2}H_2 + (k + \epsilon)H_0 + (k - \epsilon)H_3 + (k - \epsilon)D_2 + 6MG_2 = 0, \\
ia_{\mu+1/2}G_3 + 2ia_{\mu+1/2}F_1 - 2ib_{\mu-3/2}F_2 + (k + \epsilon)F_0 + (k - \epsilon)F_3 - (k + \epsilon)G_2 + 6MD_2 = 0
\end{aligned}$$

for $P_2 = P_{+1/2}$;

$$ia_{\mu-1/2}H_3 - (k + \epsilon)H_2 + 2MF_2 = 0, \quad ia_{\mu-1/2}F_0 + (k - \epsilon)F_2 + 2MH_2 = 0;$$

$P_4 = P_{-3/2}$

$$ib_{\mu+1/2}D_0 + (k - \epsilon)D_1 + 2MG_1 = 0, \quad ib_{\mu+1/2}G_3 - (k + \epsilon)G_1 + 2MD_1 = 0$$

for $P_3 = P_{+3/2}$.

5. The method by Fedorov and Groskiy

In accordance with the Fedorov – Groskiy method [21], each of the four constituents should be determined by only one function:

$$\Psi_{-1/2} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ G_0 + G_3 \\ 0 \\ D_0 + D_3 \\ F_1 \\ 0 \\ H_1 \\ 0 \\ -iF_1 \\ 0 \\ -iH_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ G_0 - G_3 \\ 0 \\ D_0 - D_3 \end{pmatrix} f_{-1/2}(r), \quad \Psi_{+1/2} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} F_0 + F_3 \\ 0 \\ H_0 + H_3 \\ 0 \\ G_2 \\ 0 \\ D_2 \\ 0 \\ iG_2 \\ 0 \\ iD_2 \\ F_0 - F_3 \\ 0 \\ H_0 - H_3 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} f_{+1/2}(r), \quad (5.1)$$

$$\Psi_{+3/2} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ F_2 \\ 0 \\ H_2 \\ 0 \\ iF_2 \\ 0 \\ iH_2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} f_{+3/2}(r), \quad \Psi_{-3/2} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ G_1 \\ 0 \\ D_1 \\ 0 \\ -iG_1 \\ 0 \\ -iD_1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} f_{-3/2}(r). \quad (5.2)$$

Consequently, the above four systems take the form

$$ib_{\mu-1/2}H_0f_{+1/2} + H_1f_{-1/2}(k - \epsilon) + 2MG_0f_{-1/2} = 0,$$

$$-ib_{\mu-1/2}F_3f_{+1/2} + F_1f_{-1/2}(k + \epsilon) + 2MD_3f_{-1/2} = 0,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& ib_{\mu-1/2}H_3f_{+1/2} - ia_{\mu+3/2}D_1f_{-3/2} + ib_{\mu-1/2}D_2f_{+1/2} \\
& -(k + \epsilon)H_1f_{-1/2} + 2(k + \epsilon)D_0f_{-1/2} + 2(k - \epsilon)D_3f_{-1/2} + 6MG_3f_{-1/2} = 0, \\
& ib_{\mu-1/2}H_3f_{+1/2} + 2ia_{\mu+3/2}D_1f_{-3/2} - 2ib_{\mu-1/2}D_2f_{+1/2} \\
& -(k + \epsilon)H_1f_{-1/2} - (k + \epsilon)D_0f_{-1/2} + (\epsilon - k)D_3f_{-1/2} + 6MF_1f_{-1/2} = 0, \\
& -ib_{\mu-1/2}F_0f_{+1/2} - ia_{\mu+3/2}G_1f_{-3/2} + ib_{\mu-1/2}G_2f_{+1/2} \\
& -(k - \epsilon)F_1f_{-1/2} - 2(k + \epsilon)G_0f_{-1/2} - 2(k - \epsilon)G_3f_{-1/2} + 6MD_0f_{-1/2} = 0, \\
& ib_{\mu-1/2}F_0f_{+1/2} - 2ia_{\mu+3/2}G_1f_{-3/2} + 2ib_{\mu-1/2}G_2f_{+1/2} \\
& +(k - \epsilon)F_1f_{-1/2} - (k + \epsilon)G_0f_{-1/2} - (k - \epsilon)G_3f_{-1/2} + 6MH_1f_{-1/2} = 0
\end{aligned}$$

for $P_1 = P_{-1/2}$;

$$\begin{aligned}
& ia_{\mu+1/2}D_3f_{-1/2} - (k + \epsilon)D_2f_{+1/2} + 2MF_3f_{+1/2} = 0, \\
& -ia_{\mu+1/2}G_0f_{-1/2} - (k - \epsilon)G_2f_{+1/2} + 2MH_0f_{+1/2} = 0, \\
& ia_{\mu+1/2}D_0f_{-1/2} + ia_{\mu+1/2}H_1f_{-1/2} - ib_{\mu-3/2}H_2f_{+3/2} \\
& -2(k + \epsilon)H_0f_{+1/2} - 2(k - \epsilon)H_3f_{+1/2} + (k - \epsilon)D_2f_{+1/2} + 6MF_0f_{+1/2} = 0, \\
& ia_{\mu+1/2}D_0f_{-1/2} - 2ia_{\mu+1/2}H_1f_{-1/2} + 2ib_{\mu-3/2}H_2f_{+3/2} \\
& +(k + \epsilon)H_0f_{+1/2} + (k - \epsilon)H_3f_{+1/2} + (k - \epsilon)D_2f_{+1/2} + 6MG_2f_{+1/2} = 0, \\
& -ia_{\mu+1/2}G_3f_{-1/2} + ia_{\mu+1/2}F_1f_{-1/2} - ib_{\mu-3/2}F_2f_{+3/2} \\
& +2(k + \epsilon)F_0f_{+1/2} + 2(k - \epsilon)F_3f_{+1/2} + (k + \epsilon)G_2f_{+1/2} + 6MH_3f_{+1/2} = 0, \\
& ia_{\mu+1/2}G_3f_{-1/2} + 2ia_{\mu+1/2}F_1f_{-1/2} - 2ib_{\mu-3/2}F_2f_{+3/2} \\
& +(k + \epsilon)F_0f_{+1/2} + (k - \epsilon)F_3f_{+1/2} - (k + \epsilon)G_2f_{+1/2} + 6MD_2f_{+1/2} = 0
\end{aligned}$$

for $P_2 = P_{+1/2}$;

$$\begin{aligned}
& ia_{\mu-1/2}H_3f_{+1/2} - (k + \epsilon)H_2f_{+3/2} + 2MF_2f_{+3/2} = 0, \\
& ia_{\mu-1/2}F_0f_{+1/2} + (k - \epsilon)F_2f_{+3/2} + 2MH_2f_{+3/2} = 0;
\end{aligned}$$

$P_4 = P_{-3/2}$

$$\begin{aligned}
& ib_{\mu+1/2}D_0f_{-1/2} + (k - \epsilon)D_1f_{-3/2} + 2MG_1f_{-3/2} = 0, \\
& ib_{\mu+1/2}G_3f_{-1/2} - (k + \epsilon)G_1f_{-3/2} + 2MD_1f_{-3/2} = 0
\end{aligned}$$

$P_3 = P_{+3/2}$.

In accordance with the general method consistent with the differential constraints [21], the obtained systems of equations must be

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\mu-1/2}f_{+1/2} &= C_1f_{+3/2}, b_{\mu-3/2}f_{+3/2} = C_2f_{+1/2}, \\ a_{\mu+1/2}f_{-1/2} &= C_3f_{+1/2}, b_{\mu-1/2}f_{+1/2} = C_4f_{-1/2}, \\ a_{\mu+3/2}f_{-3/2} &= C_5f_{-1/2}, b_{\mu+1/2}f_{-1/2} = C_6f_{-3/2}; \end{aligned}$$

all 6 parameters have the dimension of the inverse length, $[C_i] = [M] = 1/\text{meter}$. These equations yield second order equations for 4 separate functions

$$\begin{aligned} a_{\mu-1/2}b_{\mu-3/2}f_{+3/2} &= C_1 C_2 f_{+3/2}, \\ b_{\mu-3/2}a_{\mu-1/2}f_{+1/2} &= C_1 C_2 f_{+1/2}, \\ a_{\mu+1/2}b_{\mu-1/2}f_{+1/2} &= C_3 C_4 f_{+1/2}, \\ b_{\mu-1/2}a_{\mu+1/2}f_{-1/2} &= C_3 C_4 f_{-1/2}, \\ a_{\mu+3/2}b_{\mu+1/2}f_{-1/2} &= C_5 C_6 f_{-1/2}, \\ b_{\mu+1/2}a_{\mu+3/2}f_{-3/2} &= C_5 C_6 f_{-3/2}. \end{aligned} \tag{5.3}$$

Taking into account the linearity of the equations, it is easy to understand that within each of the pairs C_1, C_2 ; C_3, C_4 ; C_5, C_6 the parameters can be chosen the same

$$C_2 = C_1, \quad C_4 = C_3, \quad C_6 = C_5;$$

therefore, instead of (5.3) we have the following equations (grouping them in pairs):

$$\begin{aligned} [a_{\mu-1/2}b_{\mu-3/2} - C_1^2] f_{+3/2} &= 0, \\ [b_{\mu+1/2}a_{\mu+3/2} - C_5^2] f_{-3/2} &= 0, \\ [b_{\mu-3/2}a_{\mu-1/2} - C_1^2] f_{+1/2} &= 0, \\ [a_{\mu+1/2}b_{\mu-1/2} - C_3^2] f_{+1/2} &= 0, \\ [b_{\mu-1/2}a_{\mu+1/2} - C_3^2] f_{-1/2} &= 0, \\ [a_{\mu+3/2}b_{\mu+1/2} - C_5^2] f_{-1/2} &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

According to the equations in the second and third lines, the parameters C_1^2 and C_3^2 must be related, as well as parameters C_3^2 and C_5^2 .

Let us find the explicit form of second order operators in eqs. (5.4); hence, we obtain the relationships between parameters:

$$\begin{aligned} -C_3^2 = +2B - C_1^2 &\implies C_1^2 = C_3^2 + 2B, \\ -C_3^2 = -2B - C_5^2 &\implies C_5^2 = C_3^2 - 2B. \end{aligned} \tag{5.5}$$

We will consider parameter C_3^2 as the primary one, denoting it as X ; it has the dimension of the square of inverse length, $[X] = [B] = 1/L^2$.

So, there are only 4 different equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{1}{4} B^2 r^2 - \frac{(m-3/2)^2}{r^2} \right. \\ \left. - B(m + \frac{3}{2}) - X \right] f_{+3/2} &= 0, \\ \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{1}{4} B^2 r^2 - \frac{(m+3/2)^2}{r^2} \right. \\ \left. - B(m - \frac{3}{2}) - X \right] f_{-3/2} &= 0; \end{aligned} \tag{5.6}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{1}{4} B^2 r^2 - \frac{(m-1/2)^2}{r^2} \right. \\ \left. - B(m + \frac{1}{2}) - X \right] f_{+1/2} &= 0, \\ \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{1}{4} B^2 r^2 - \frac{(m+1/2)^2}{r^2} \right. \\ \left. - B(m - \frac{1}{2}) - X \right] f_{-1/2} &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{5.7}$$

6. Solving the second order equations

We start with equations (5.6) and (5.7). Let us consider the first equation from (5.6):

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{1}{4} B^2 r^2 \right. \\ \left. - \frac{(m-3/2)^2}{r^2} - B(m+3/2) - X \right] f_{+3/2} &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

in the new variable $r^2 = x$, it reads

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{x} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{B^2}{16} - \frac{(m-3/2)^2}{4x^2} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{B(m+3/2) + X}{4x} \right] f_{+3/2} &= 0. \end{aligned} \tag{6.1}$$

This equation refers to confluent hypergeometric type. Let us find behavior of solutions near the point $x = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{x} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{(m-3/2)^2}{4x^2} \right] f_{+3/2} &= 0, \\ f_{+3/2} &= x^A, \quad A = \pm \frac{|m-3/2|}{2}; \end{aligned} \tag{6.2}$$

to describe the bound states, we need solutions regular at zero, therefore we will use the positive values for A . Let us find behavior of the solutions at infinity (assuming $B > 0$)

$$\left[\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{x} \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{B^2}{16} \right] f_{+3/2} = 0$$

to describe the bound states. Here $f_{+3/2} = e^{Dx}$, $D = \pm \frac{B}{4}$. Further, we use the negative values for D . Searching solutions in the form $f_{+3/2} = x^A e^{Dx} F_{+3/2}(x)$ we derive equation for $F_{+3/2}$ (we choose the parameters A and D as follow $A = +\frac{|m-3/2|}{2}$, $D = -\frac{B}{4}$):

$$\left[x \frac{d^2}{dx^2} + [(2A + 1) + 2Dx] \frac{d}{dx} - \frac{B(m + 3/2) + X - 4D(2A + 1)}{4} \right] F_{+3/2} = 0.$$

In new variable $2Dx = -z$, equation reads

$$z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} F_{+3/2} + (2A + 1 - z) \frac{d}{dz} F_{+3/2} - \frac{(m + 3/2) + (2A + 1) + X/B}{2} F_{+3/2} = 0.$$

Taking into account the identity $2A + 1 = + |m - 3/2| + 1$, the equation may be re-written as

$$z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} F_{+3/2} + \left(|m - 3/2| + 1 - z \right) \frac{d}{dz} F_{+3/2} - \left(\frac{(m + 3/2) + |m - 3/2| + 1}{2} + \frac{X}{2B} \right) F_{+3/2} = 0,$$

it coincides with the confluent hypergeometric equation, $z f'' + (\gamma - z) f' - \alpha f = 0$. As a quantization rule we use the polynomial condition, $\alpha = -n$:

$$\frac{(m + 3/2) + |m - 3/2| + 1}{2} + n_1 + \frac{X}{2B} = 0.$$

With notation

$$N_1 = \frac{(m + 3/2) + |m - 3/2| + 1}{2} + n_1,$$

the quantization rule is written as

$$X = -2BN_1 < 0. \tag{6.3}$$

Analyzing the second equation from (5.6) by similar method, we derive

$$f_{-3/2} = x^{A'} e^{D'x} F_{-3/2},$$

$$A' = + \frac{|m + 3/2|}{2}, D' = -\frac{B}{4},$$

$$z \frac{d^2}{dz^2} F_{-3/2} + \left(|m + 3/2| + 1 - z \right) \frac{d}{dz} F_{-3/2} - \left(\frac{(m - 3/2) + |m + 3/2| + 1}{2} + \frac{X}{2B} \right) F_{-3/2}(z) = 0,$$

The quantization rule has the form

$$\frac{(m - 3/2) + |m + 3/2| + 1}{2} + n_2 + \frac{X}{2B} = 0 \tag{6.4}$$

or differently

$$N_2 = \frac{m - 3/2 + |m + 3/2| + 1}{2} + n, X = -2BN_2.$$

Now we turn to the second pair of equations (5.7), they differ from equations of first pair (5.7) by following changes

$$|m - 3/2| \implies |m - 1/2|, m + 3/2 \implies m + 1/2;$$

$$|m + 3/2| \implies |m + 1/2|, m - 3/2 \implies m - 1/2,$$

so no additional calculations are needed.

Therefore, for equations (5.6)–(5.7) we have the following quantization rules:

$$F_{+3/2}, N_1 = \frac{(m + 3/2) + |m - 3/2| + 1}{2} + n_1;$$

$$F_{-3/2}, N_2 = \frac{(m - 3/2) + |m + 3/2| + 1}{2} + n_2;$$

$$F_{+1/2}, N_3 = \frac{(m + 1/2) + |m - 1/2| + 1}{2} + n_3;$$

$$F_{-1/2}, N_4 = \frac{(m - 1/2) + |m + 1/2| + 1}{2} + n_4.$$

The value X is the same for all four cases, so we can use the first variant.

7. Solutions for algebraic system, specifying the energy spectra

Taking into account conditions (5.3) in the system of differential equations, we obtain the following algebraic equations

$$\begin{aligned}
 & iC_3H_0 + (k - \epsilon)H_1 + 2MG_0 = 0, \quad -iC_3F_3 + (k + \epsilon)F_1 + 2MD_3 = 0, \\
 & iC_3H_3 - iC_5D_1 + iC_3D_2 - (k + \epsilon)H_1 + 2(k + \epsilon)D_0 + 2(k - \epsilon)D_3 + 6MG_3 = 0, \\
 & iC_3H_3 + 2iC_5D_1 - 2iC_3D_2 - (k + \epsilon)H_1 - (k + \epsilon)D_0 + (\epsilon - k)D_3 + 6MF_1 = 0, \\
 & -iC_3F_0 - iC_5G_1 + iC_3G_2 - (k - \epsilon)F_1 - 2(k + \epsilon)G_0 - 2(k - \epsilon)G_3 + 6MD_0 = 0, \\
 & iC_3F_0 - 2iC_5G_1 + 2iC_3G_2 + (k - \epsilon)F_1 - (k + \epsilon)G_0 - (k - \epsilon)G_3 + 6MH_1 = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

for $P_1 = P_{-1/2}$;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & iC_3D_3 - (k + \epsilon)D_2 + 2MF_3 = 0, \quad -iC_3G_0 - (k - \epsilon)G_2 + 2MH_0 = 0, \\
 & iC_3D_0 + iC_3H_1 - iC_1H_2 - 2(k + \epsilon)H_0 - 2(k - \epsilon)H_3 + (k - \epsilon)D_2 + 6MF_0 = 0, \\
 & iC_3D_0 - 2iC_3H_1 + 2iC_1H_2 + (k + \epsilon)H_0 + (k - \epsilon)H_3 + (k - \epsilon)D_2 + 6MG_2 = 0, \\
 & -iC_3G_3 + iC_3F_1 - iC_1F_2 + 2(k + \epsilon)F_0 + 2(k - \epsilon)F_3 + (k + \epsilon)G_2 + 6MH_3 = 0, \\
 & iC_3G_3 + 2iC_3F_1 - 2iC_1F_2 + (k + \epsilon)F_0 + (k - \epsilon)F_3 - (k + \epsilon)G_2 + 6MD_2 = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

for $P_2 = P_{+1/2}$;

$$iC_1H_3 - (k + \epsilon)H_2 + 2MF_2 = 0, \quad iC_1F_0 + (k - \epsilon)F_2 + 2MH_2 = 0$$

for $P_3 = P_{+3/2}$;

$$iC_5D_0 + (k - \epsilon)D_1 + 2MG_1 = 0, \quad iC_5G_3 - (k + \epsilon)G_1 + 2MD_1 = 0$$

for $P_4 = P_{-3/2}$.

It should be noted that when extracting square roots, two possibilities arise in each case

$$C_3 = \delta_3\sqrt{X} = i\delta_3\sqrt{2BN}, \delta_3^2 = 1; \quad C_1 = \delta_1i\sqrt{2B(N-1)}, \delta_1^2 = 1; \quad C_5 = i\delta_5\sqrt{2B(N+1)}, \delta_5^2 = 1.$$

It may be shown that all 8 possibilities are equivalent to the simplest one when $\delta_1 = \delta_3 = \delta_5 = +1$ (we omit details of the proof). Let us find the homogenous system of 16 equations

$$A_{16 \times 16}X = 0, \quad X = \text{columb}(F_0, F_1, F_2, F_3; G_0, G_1, G_2, G_3; H_0, H_1, H_2, H_3; D_0, D_1, D_2, D_3);$$

the main matrix is found explicitly (we omit its expression). The main matrix depends on four parameters M, ϵ, k, B ; besides we have the relations

$$C_1 = +\sqrt{X + 2B}, \quad C_3 = +\sqrt{X}, \quad C_5 = +\sqrt{X - 2B}, \quad X = -2BN \quad (\text{let } \sqrt{X} = Y).$$

Taking into account these relations, we can obtain in explicit form the main matrix $A_{16 \times 16}$ (for brevity we omit its presentation). The vanishing of its determinant leads to the following 8-order algebraic equation with respect to Y :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \det A = & 1679616M^8Y^8 + 1296 \left(-20736M^{10} - 5184k^2M^8 + 5184\epsilon^2M^8 + 288B^2M^6 + 72B^2k^2M^4 - 72B^2\epsilon^2M^4 \right) Y^6 \\
 & + 1296 \left(124416M^{12} + 62208k^2M^{10} - 62208\epsilon^2M^{10} + 7776k^4M^8 + 7776\epsilon^4M^8 \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - 3456B^2M^8 - 15552k^2\epsilon^2M^8 - 288B^2k^2M^6 \right) Y^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +288B^2\epsilon^2M^6 + 16B^4M^4 - 216B^2k^4M^4 - 216B^2\epsilon^4M^4 + 432B^2k^2\epsilon^2M^4 + 8B^4k^2M^2 \\
& \quad - 8B^4\epsilon^2M^2 + B^4k^4 + B^4\epsilon^4 - 2B^4k^2\epsilon^2)Y^4 \\
& +1296\left(-331776M^{14} - 248832k^2M^{12} + 248832\epsilon^2M^{12} - 62208k^4M^{10} - 62208\epsilon^4M^{10} + 13824B^2M^{10} + \right. \\
& \quad +124416k^2\epsilon^2M^{10} - 5184k^6M^8 + 5184\epsilon^6M^8 - 15552k^2\epsilon^4M^8 - 1152B^2k^2M^8 + 15552k^4\epsilon^2M^8 + \\
& \quad +1152B^2\epsilon^2M^8 - 128B^4M^6 - 288B^2k^4M^6 - 288B^2\epsilon^4M^6 + 576B^2k^2\epsilon^2M^6 + 216B^2k^6M^4 - 216B^2\epsilon^6M^4 + \\
& \quad \left. +648B^2k^2\epsilon^4M^4 - 648B^2k^4\epsilon^2M^4 - 2B^4k^6 + 2B^4\epsilon^6 - 6B^4k^2\epsilon^4 + 6B^4k^4\epsilon^2\right)Y^2 \\
& +1296\left(331776M^{16} + 331776k^2M^{14} - 331776\epsilon^2M^{14} + 124416k^4M^{12} + 124416\epsilon^4M^{12} - 18432B^2M^{12} - 248832k^2\epsilon^2M^{12} + \right. \\
& \quad +20736k^6M^{10} - 20736\epsilon^6M^{10} + 62208k^2\epsilon^4M^{10} + 4608B^2k^2M^{10} - 62208k^4\epsilon^2M^{10} - 4608B^2\epsilon^2M^{10} + \\
& \quad +1296k^8M^8 + 1296\epsilon^8M^8 - 5184k^2\epsilon^6M^8 + 256B^4M^8 + 4608B^2k^4M^8 + 7776k^4\epsilon^4M^8 + \\
& \quad +4608B^2\epsilon^4M^8 - 5184k^6\epsilon^2M^8 - 9216B^2k^2\epsilon^2M^8 + 288B^2k^6M^6 - 288B^2\epsilon^6M^6 + 864B^2k^2\epsilon^4M^6 - 128B^4k^2M^6 + \\
& \quad +128B^4\epsilon^2M^6 - 864B^2k^4\epsilon^2M^6 - 72B^2k^8M^4 - 72B^2\epsilon^8M^4 + 288B^2k^2\epsilon^6M^4 + \\
& \quad +48B^4k^4M^4 + 48B^4\epsilon^4M^4 - 432B^2k^4\epsilon^4M^4 + 288B^2k^6\epsilon^2M^4 - 96B^4k^2\epsilon^2M^4 - 8B^4k^6M^2 + \\
& \quad \left. +8B^4\epsilon^6M^2 - 24B^4k^2\epsilon^4M^2 + 24B^4k^4\epsilon^2M^2 + B^4k^8 + B^4\epsilon^8 - 4B^4k^2\epsilon^6 + 6B^4k^4\epsilon^4 - 4B^4k^6\epsilon^2\right) = 0.
\end{aligned}$$

This equation contains the powers Y^8, Y^6, Y^4, Y^2, Y^0 ; in variable $Y^2 = X$ we derive the fourth order equation. Using the notation $E^2 = \epsilon^2 - k^2 > 0$, we present the 4 solutions in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
X_1 &= \frac{2B^2(E^2 - M^2) - 2B\sqrt{B^2(E^2 - M^2)^2 - 6BM^3E(E^2 - M^2) + 36M^6E^2 + 3M^3E} - 9M^4(E^2 - M^2)}{9M^4}, \\
X_2 &= \frac{2B^2(E^2 - M^2) + 2B\sqrt{B^2(E^2 - M^2)^2 - 6BM^3E(E^2 - M^2) + 36M^6E^2 - 3M^3E} - 9M^4(E^2 - M^2)}{9M^4}, \\
X_3 &= \frac{2B^2(E^2 - M^2) - 2B\sqrt{B^2(E^2 - M^2)^2 + 6BM^3E(E^2 - M^2) + 36M^6E^2 - 3M^3E} - 9M^4(E^2 - M^2)}{9M^4}, \\
X_4 &= \frac{2B^2(E^2 - M^2) + 2B\sqrt{B^2(E^2 - M^2)^2 + 6BM^3E(E^2 - M^2) + 36M^6E^2 + 3M^3E} - 9M^4(E^2 - M^2)}{9M^4}.
\end{aligned}$$

The expressions for all X_i should be equated to the same value: $X_i = -2BN$. It is convenient to apply the dimensionless quantities

$$W = E/M, \quad b = B/M^2, \quad x_i = X_i/M^2; \quad (7.1)$$

then the formulas for roots are written shorter

$$\begin{aligned}
x_1 &= \frac{1}{9}\left(2b^2(W^2 - 1) - 2b\sqrt{b^2(W^2 - 1)^2 - 6b(W^2 - 1)W + 36W^2} - 6bW - 9W^2 + 9\right), \\
x_2 &= \frac{1}{9}\left(2b^2(W^2 - 1) + 2b\sqrt{b^2(W^2 - 1)^2 - 6b(W^2 - 1)W + 36W^2} - 6bW - 9W^2 + 9\right), \\
x_3 &= \frac{1}{9}\left(2b^2(W^2 - 1) - 2b\sqrt{b^2(W^2 - 1)^2 + 6b(W^2 - 1)W + 36W^2} + 6bW - 9W^2 + 9\right), \\
x_4 &= \frac{1}{9}\left(2b^2(W^2 - 1) + 2b\sqrt{b^2(W^2 - 1)^2 + 6b(W^2 - 1)W + 36W^2} + 6bW - 9W^2 + 9\right).
\end{aligned} \quad (7.2)$$

The formulas (7.2) can be resolved with respect to the variable W , so we obtain

$$(36 - b^2)W^4 + 24bW^3 + W^2(2b(b^2 - 72)N - 4(b^2 + 72))$$

$$- 48bW(bN + 2) - 8(b^2 - 18bN - 36)(bN + 2) = 0,$$

$$(36 - b^2)W^4 - 24bW^3 + W^2(2b(b^2 - 72)N - 4(b^2 + 72))$$

$$+ 48bW(bN + 2) - 8(b^2 - 18bN - 36)(bN + 2) = 0.$$

Note that these equations differ from each other by formal change, $W \Rightarrow -W$; this means that it is enough to consider only the first equation.

Explicit expressions for the roots are cumbersome, by this reason we have analyzed them numerically. Let us write out the tables of values for W_1^2 , W_2^2 , W_3^2 , W_3^2 . For numerical calculations we have used the following values for b : 1, 5, 10, 20; the parameter N takes values from 1 to 30 in step of 1.

As a result, we numerically have shown that 4 series of real-valued energy spectra can

exist, and all remaining ones provide us with non-interpretable complex-valued energies which should be ignored, they correspond to so called anomalous solutions.

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